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PARAMETRIC DIFFERENCE IN TERMS OF CONTIGUOUS RELATIONS.

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Abstract:

Here we have defined a parametric difference ($/\Delta$) on a hypergeometric series and found the n^{th} difference of contiguous relations. We have taken special case ${}_2F_1$. This parametric difference also shown in terms of contiguous relations.

1 -Introduction

The idea of extending the number of Parameters in the hypergeometric function seems to have occurred for the first time, in the work of Gauss (1828). He introduced a series with three numerator parameters and two denominator parameters. . Over the next hundred years the well known set of special summation theorems associated with the names of Gauss (1800) Dixon (1903) and Dougall’s (1907) were developed these are all for series in which $A= B+1$ and $Z=1$. It can be shown that Dougall , s theorem, giving the sum of a ${}_7F_6$ Series, is the most general possible theorem of this kind, the whole theory as it existed then was analysed exhaustively and brought to perfection by W.N.Bailey, in a long series of Papers during the decades of 1920-50. Indeed at this time L.J. Rogers is reported to have said” Nothing remains to be done in the field of hypergeometric series.

The whole theory of the general function ${}_A F_B (Z)$ was still untouched. The first attempts at a general transformation theory were already being made by Whipple (1934,1937) and the concept of the asymptotic expansions for the function were already implicit in the work of Barnes (1970a).

2- Formulations:

- i. $F = F(a,b; c; z)$
- ii $F(1) = F(a+1, b+1; c+1; Z)$

$$\text{iii. } \Delta F = F(1^+) - F$$

$$\text{iv. } [(c; a; b); n] = [A, n] = \frac{(c)_n}{(a)_n (b)_n}$$

$$\text{v. Particular case } [A, 0] = 1$$

$$\text{vi. } F = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[A, n] z^n}{n!}$$

$$\text{vii. } D \equiv \frac{d}{dz}$$

2.1 Theorem: For hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z)$

$$\Delta^n F = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} [A, r] (-1)^{n-r} D^r F$$

Proof: Let

$$\Delta F = F(a+1, b+1; c; z) - F(a, b; c; z)$$

$$\Delta \equiv [A, 1] D - [A, 0]$$

$$\Delta^2 F = \Delta [\Delta F]$$

$$\Delta^2 \equiv [A, 1] D^2 - {}^2c_1 [A, 1] D + {}^2c_2 [A, 0] D^0$$

$$\Delta^3 \equiv [A, 3] D^3 - {}^3c_1 [A, 2] D^2 + {}^3c_2 [A, 1] D - [A, 0]$$

Similarly

$$\Delta^n \equiv [A, n] D^n - {}^nc_1 [A, n-1] D^{n-1} + {}^nc_2 [A, n-2] D^{n-2} - \dots + (-1)^n [A, 0]$$

Or

$$\Delta^n \equiv \sum_{r=0}^n [A, r] (-1)^{n-r} D^r$$

Hence

$$\Delta^n F = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} [A, r] (-1)^{n-r} D^r F$$

Contiguous relations:

3.1 Theorem: To prove that ${}_{\Delta}^n F(a, b; c; z) = F[n^+] - {}^n c_1 F[(n-1)^+] + {}^n c_2 F[(n-2)^+] - {}^n c_3 F[(n-3)^+] + \dots + (-1)^n F$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} {}_{\Delta} F(a, b; c; z) &= F[1^+] - F \\ {}_{\Delta}^2 F &= F[2^+] - 2F[1^+] + F \\ {}_{\Delta}^3 F &= F[3^+] - 2F[2^+] + 3F[1^+] - F \\ {}_{\Delta}^4 F &= F[4^+] - 4F[3^+] + 6F[2^+] - 4F[1^+] + F \end{aligned}$$

Similarly

$${}_{\Delta}^n F(a, b; c; z) = F[n^+] - {}^n c_1 F[(n-1)^+] + {}^n c_2 F[(n-2)^+] - {}^n c_3 F[(n-3)^+] + \dots + (-1)^n F$$

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